

Measuring The Self-Sufficiency Ratio And The Size Of Food Gap (Shortage) From Food In Al-Anbar Governorate

Nabeel Taha Ali Belal , Khalid Akbar Abdullah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: July 22, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: February 23, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Self- Sufficiency Food, AL-Anbar, Governorate</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6249535</p>	<p><i>The agricultural production in two branches vegetal and animal represents an importance in providing the population needs from food locally with high auality and in the appropriate time, therefore we will focus in this research on measuring the self- sufficiency(1)*. of in Al-Anbar governorate with appointing the food gap(2)**. because of dissimilarity between surplus and shortage for vegetal and animal productions within Al-Anbar governorate after determining the size of individual consuming in one year from food as it explained in table(1), and an age group is excluded because it is not within the actual yearly consumption for food. We excluele children of two years age or younger They are (175269) people living in (22) administrative units and the whole size of consumer people in Al-Anbar governorate (1690549) people of the whole population (1865818) people according to estimation of 2020 ad(3). the self-sufficiency and food gap for agricultural products is talked over and it shows that the governorate has sufficiency with some vegetarian productions like (wheat, corn, vegetables, dates onions and tubers) whereas a food gap (shortage) is registered for (barley, fruit, legumes and oil crops), As for animal production it registered a food gap (shortage) for all animal production and the reason is clue to the lack of agricultural and animal investment which has a negative effect on self-sufficiency of food in Al-Anbar governorate.</i></p>

Introduction

The research problem is centered in the following question:- Is there a food gap (shortage) in Al-Anbar governorate for agricultural products (plant-animal), what is the rate of self-sufficiency for these products.

Research thesis

There is a food gap(shortage) for some agricultural products and a food gap(shortage) for all animal products and it vary between one king and another for these products, whereas some plant products achieved a rate of self-sufficiency for products like (wheat, corn, vegetables, fruit, onions, and tubers).

The research goal

The Research goal is to measure the size of the food gap(shortage) and the rate of self-sufficiency for agricultural products (plants – animals) in AL-Anbar governorate.

The research limits

AL-Anbar governorate astronomically lies between latitude (35.15-30.33) north and longitude (44.10-38.40) east, its geographical location is on the west part of Iraq, from the north there is Nineveh governorate, to the north east there is Salah AL-Anbar governorate to the east there are Baghdad Babil governorate Karballah governorate to the south east there is AL-Anjaf governorate, to the south there is Saudi Arabia, to the west and north west there are Jordan and Syria as it showed in map (1) and (2).

Map (1) The astronomical location of AL-Anbar province

Resource: General Authority for Survey, the administrative map of Iraq scale 1: 1000000 for the year 2020.

Map (2) Administrative borders of AL-Anbar governorate

Resource: General Authority for Survey, Anbar Governorate Topographic Map Scale 1: 100000 for the year 2020.

The research main points

1- Plant production

Production is the result of the natural and human abilities that provide the the necessary food for people and that vary as a group of crops like (grain crop, vegetables, fruits, dates, onion, tubers, legumes and oil crops) which we explain as follows :

1-2- grains

Grains are divided into:

1-2-1- wheat

Wheat is a main food for daily use by people. The rate of consumption of wheat during the year 2020 (147) kg / year as it is explained in table (1) and Figure (1) The governorate production of wheat in that year was (256547) ton, while consumption amount (246816) ton, which means that there was surplus a bout (9731) tons and the rate of the governorate sufficiency of wheat was a bout (104%). The governorate doesn't suffer from food gap as it is explained in table (2) and Figure (2).

Table (1). The rate of consumption for individual person from food (kg / year) for Iraq population 2020.

No	Plant products	The rate of consumption for individual person kg	NO	The animal products	The rate of consumption for individual person kg
1	Wheat	146	1	Red meat	12
2	Barley	7	2	Chicken	10
3	Corn	9	3	Eggs	132
4	Vegetables	150	4	Milk	52
5	Fruits	76	5	Fish	9
6	Bates	12	6	Honey	(300)gram
7	Onions and tubers	56		-	-
8	Legumes	6		-	-
9	Oil crops	12		-	-

Resource: according to ministry of planning and deve lopment cooperation, central statistical organization, family survey department 2020, unpublished data

Figure (1). The rate of consumption for individual person from food (kg / year) for Iraq population 2020.

Chest: drawing on the table (1).

Figure (2). The rate of self-sufficiency and food gap for agricultural crops in AL-Anbar governorate 2020 ad.

Chest: drawing on the table (2).

According to what was mentioned we see that the reason for the self-sufficiency is due to the expansion in growing wheat and the rise of production is larger than the yearly human consumption rate of wheat because of the exploitation of the natural and human abilities.

Table (2). The rate of self-sufficiency and food gap for agricultural crops in AL-Anbar governorate 2020 ad.

NO	Crop	Planted area/ acres	Yield kg/acres	Production/ton	Consumption rate/ton	Food gap(shortage)/ton	Self-sufficiency rate
1	Wheat	295552	868	256539	246816	9731	%104
2	Barley	14227	438.8	6242	11835	5593	%53
3	Corn	30284	548.7	16617	15215	1402	%109
4	Vegetables	101320	2921.4	295998	253582	42416	%117
5	Fruits	610059	25	15351	128482	113131	%12
6	Bates	906982	81.4	73828	20286	53542	%363
7	Onions and tubers	50368	4007	201824	94671	107153	%213
8	Legumes	14275	432	6166	10143	3977	%61
9	Oil crops	19863	390.3	7753	20286	12533	%38

Resource: researcher work depending on: ministry of agriculture, Agriculture directorate of AL-Anbar governorate planning and follow-up department 2020, unpublished data.

1-2-2 barley

Barley has a big importance because it is used as food for people and as fodder for animals. The need for barley is increasing. From table(2) and Figure (2) the production of barley during the year 2020 in AL-Anbar governorate is (6242) tons versus a consumption rate (11835) tons and the size of food gap (shortage) is (5593) tons and the rate of self-sufficiency in the whole governorate is (53%) the reason behind the little production for this crop is using this crop as a fodder animals which effect in the amounts of production grains.

3-corn

The corn is an important grain that is used for making human food. It is used as a flour. Cornstarch, oil and it is used in making concentrated feed for coms and poultry as well as using its remains as a dry green fodder⁽⁴⁾, from the table(2) and Figure (2) it is clear that the production of corn in AL-Anbar governorate for the year 2020 is (16617) tons versus it a consumption rate about (15215) tons and the governorate doesn't suffer from food gap (shortage) on the contrary there is increasing in production rate versus the consumption rate a bout (1402) tons and the rate of self-sufficiency for the governorate is a bout (109%).

1-3 Second / vegetables

vegetables have a big importance in human food because they contain the important nutrients like vitamins, proteins and metallic elements like calcium, potassium and phosphorous. They grow them in tow periods summer and winter⁽⁵⁾ The production of the governorate of vegetables in 2020 is (295998)tons as it shown in table (2) and Figure(2) whereas the rate of the whole consumption of the governorate is (2533582) tons with a rate of consumption (150) kg / year for as it shown in table(1). The surplus of production is (42416) ton which means that the governorate doesn't suffer from food gap (shortage)in the contrary the governorate achieved a rate of self-sufficiency about (117%). The reason behind the self- sufficiency for vegetables is because of expansion in growing vegetables because of the continuous need vegetables.

1-4 Fruits and dates

1-4-1 Fruits

Fruits consider and from food that have high nutritional value due to what they have like sugary substances, oils, mineral salts, proteins, vitamins as well as they bring money to the farmer so many countries grow fruit trees to develobe their economy. The demand for fruits vary according to the nature of consumption of population⁽⁶⁾.

Therefore the rate of individual consumption for fruits in 2020 is (76)kg / year as its explained in table (1) The production of AL-Anbar governorate of fruit in 2020 about (15351) tons whereas the consumption is (128482) tons recording a food gab (shortage) of about (113131) tons. The self-sufficiency rate for the whole governorate is (12%) as its explained in table(2) and Figure(2). Through the foregoing it is clear that the self-sufficiency rate is few with the presence of a food gap (shortage) and the reason of that is the fewness of fruit trees with few production of every tree as well as low production with the increasing of yearly consumption rate of fruits by people which reflect on self-sufficiency of fruit while there is a shortage in some kindes of fruits which they are wanted widely like bananas, peach and other frutis because they need an environment which is not available in AL-Anbar governorate.

1-4-2 Date

A valuable fast easy to eat food. The sugars are most important part of dates. They represent more than (70%) form their weight. They treat anemia because they contain a high rate of iron⁽⁷⁾. The dates are food for people in AL-Anbar governorate. The individual consumption rate of dates in 2020 (12) kg / year table (1), The governorate produce (73828) tons and the consumption in the same year is (20286) ton with a surplus of (53542) tons recording a self-sufficiency rate of (364%) as it shown in table (2) and Figure(2), this increase in self-sufficiency rate of dates in AL-Anbar is because of the surplus of production to the need of consumption by people because of date palm trees and the good care of date palm farming.

1-5 Onions and tubers

Like onions, garlic, potatoes are the most used crops in food because they contain starch and protein. The individual consumption of onions and tubers in 2020 (56) kg / year as its shown in table (1). The production of onions and tuber in AL-Anbar is (201824) tons while the whole consumption rate in the governorate is (94671) tons with achieve a self-sufficiency rate. (213%) as its shown in table (2) and Figure(2), From what's mentioned it's clear that AL-Anbar governorate has a self-sufficiency of onions and tubers.

1-6 Legumes

Legumes are used in preparing many meals. They are considered as a source for protein which are cheaper than animal protein. They are important for people who don't eat meat. They are also used as a fodder for animals⁽⁸⁾. The consumption rate for an individual of legumes is (6) kg / year while the governorate production is (6166) tons during the year 2020. The consumption rate is (10143) and the food gap (shortage) is (-3977) tons. The governorate sufficiency is (61%), as it shown in table (2) and Figure(2), The lake of growing this crop is a reason of making food gap (shortage) and not achieving self-sufficiency.

1-7 Oil crops

These crops are grown in order to get their seeds and squeeze them to make oil.⁽⁹⁾ The oil crops are sesame, sunflower and peanut. The rate of consumption for an individual for oil crops in 2020 is (12) kg / year. The production of AL-Anbar of oil crops is (7753) tons while the consumption rate is (20286) tons, versus it a food gap (shortage) a bout (-12533) tons. And the rate of the governorate sufficiency of oil crops is (38%) as it is shown in table (2) and Figure(2).

2 – Second- animal production

The animal production has many forms such as red meat (sheep, goats, and cows), white meat (chicken and fish) milk, eggs and honey which are within the daily food for people. They rich of proteins, vitamins and mineral salts. People can't dispense them as well as they are easy to digest and they have an important role in building human body⁽¹⁰⁾ We will study the animal production in AL-Anbar governorate because it is a priority of achieving self-sufficiency and provide food for people. They are divided as follows :

2-1 Red meat

Red meat is an important source of food for people to get proteins we need which is available in our country or by importing it if we can't make it. The lack of production leads to a food gap between what is available by inside production and the rate of consumption by people. The carcass is a fulcrum between the production and consumption⁽¹¹⁾ The need for meat differs. Some are slayed in massacre then they take them to markets. Some are offered for guests or offered in religious occasions or family occasions. All these make it difficult to compute the number of animals that are slayed and the amount of production is unknown. Therefore many studies went to estimate the ready to slay from the whole number of animals by accredited rates to estimate the ready number to estimate the flock.⁽¹²⁾ The number of animals in AL-Anbar governorate in 2020 (2690315) sheep, (154124) goats and (56917) cows. The number of animals to slay is (1479673) sheep, (80144) goats and (30726) of cows. The average of carcass weight is (19) kg / for sheep, (14) kg for goats and (125)kg for cows.⁽¹³⁾ The production is (28117) tons for sheep, (1121) tons of goats and (3845) tons of cows. The total production is (33083) tons, but it's better to extract the carcass net weight which is called net weight.^{(14)**} To get a net production it's for sheep (15183) tons, for goats (582) tons and for cows (2116) tons. The whole net production in AL-Anbar governorate is (17881) tons, the individual consumption from red meat is (12) kg / year as its shown in table (1). The consumption for the whole governorate is (20285)tons versus it a food gap (shortage) of about (2404)tons with arate of self-sufficiency of (88%) as its shown in table (3) and Figure(3). Through the foregoing it is clear that the governorate doesn't have self-sufficiency and it suffers from a food gap (shortage) and that need to develop the cattle numbers and to exploit all the available facilities.

2-2 Poultry

Poultry farming is a main substrate of livestock substrates due to it contributes in providing white meat as well as providing eggs. They both provides nutritional value for people which helps to submit the people needs in order to achieve the self-sufficiency.⁽¹⁵⁾ In AL-Anbar governorate poultry fields spread which are coming after in providing fodder cattle breeding. According to that poultry farming and chicken production are divided in to two parts :

2-1-2 Chicken meat production

Chicken meat has a good nutritional value due to it has nutritional elements as well as it is cheaper than red meat and that make it more wanted in local from table (1). We can see the consumption rate for an individual person of chicken meat in 2020 is (10) kg / year. The poultry farms owners prefer the chicken to weigh (2) kg in order to sell it in the market.⁽¹⁶⁾ The production of AL-Anbar

Table (3)

Measuring the size of food gap (shortage) or surplus and the rate of self-sufficiency of animal production in AL-Anbar governorate in 2020 ad.

No	Producti on kind	Number of sheep	Number of goats	Num ber of caws	Net productio n / ton	Size of consumpt ion / ton	Food gap (shortage) or surplus	Rate of self-sufficiency
1	Red meat	2690315	154124	56917	17881	20285	2404-	88%
	Producti on kind	Form numbers	Absorbing capacity	Prod uctio n/ton	Size of consumpt ion / ton	Food gap (shortage) or surplus		Rate of self-sufficiency
2	Chicken for meat	502	10308	10349	16907	6558-		%61
	Producti on kind	Form numbers	Absorbing capacity	Prod uctio n/egg	Size of consumpt ion / egg	Food gap (shortage) or surplus		Rate of self-sufficiency
3	Table eggs	51	405131	106954584	223152468	116197884-		%48
	Producti on kind	Number of sheep	Number of goats	Num ber of caws	Net productio n / ton	Size of consumpt ion / ton	Food gap (shortage) or surplus	Rate of self-sufficiency
4	Milk	2690315	154124	56917	30990	87909	56919-	%35

	Producti on kind	Aqua riums numb er	Wate r area acres	Cag es nu mbe r	Wate r area/ m3	Fishi ng area	Productio n/ ton	Consump tion/ ton	Food gap (shortage) or surplus	Rate of self- sufficiency
5	fish	241	373	894	2413 1	Euph rates ALth artha r and hade eth lake	7518	15215	7697-	%49
	Producti on kind	Beehives number	Beehive average production		productio n / kg	Size of consump tion / kg	Food gap (shortage) or surplus	Rate of self- sufficiency		
6	honey	21978	7.7		169231	507165	337934-	33%		

Resource: researcher work depending on: ministry of agriculture, Agriculture directorate of AL-Anbar governorate rate planning and follow-up department 2020, unpublished data.

Governorate in 2020 (10349) tons achieving a rate of self-sufficiency a bout (61%). The consumption is (16907) tons that means there is a food gap of about (6558)tons as its shown in table (3) and Figure(3).

Figure (3)

Measuring the self-sufficiency rate and the food gap and deficit in animal production in AL-Anbar governorate for the year 2020.

Chest: drawing on the table (3).

2-2-2 Eggs production

Eggs have many benefits. They are also good for health. They are considered a main meal for human because they contain minerals, proteins and vitamins. In one egg the protein rate is (12%) and it is a high rate by comparing it with other crops like potatoes.⁽¹⁷⁾ Therefore the demand for eggs is increasing daily. The consumption of an increasing daily. The consumption of an individual of eggs in 2020 is (132) eggs. The production of eggs in AL-Anbar governorate in 2020 is (106954584) eggs. The consumption is (223152468) eggs, the food gap (shortage) reaches (116197884) eggs with a rate of self- sufficiency about (48%) as shown in table (3) and Figure(3). Through the forgoing it's clear that AL-Anbar governorate suffers from a food gap (shortage) in producing poultry because of the lake of the producing farms and

this needs expanding poultry with the government support for farmers because all farms belong to the private sector.

Milk

Milk and its products are one of the most important food goods for people. It considers from the integrated foods because it contains calcium, proteins sugars fats and salts which human body it also. This increase the consumption of milk very much.⁽¹⁸⁾ sheep numbers in AL-Anbar are (2690315) sheep, goats (154124) and cow (56917). The number of milk females are extracted from the a group of rates.^{*(19)} The milk females for sheep are (618771), for goats are (38532) and for cows (10814). the total number of females (668117) milk production is extracted through the amount of production for each kind of cattle's, after exclusion feeding milk.^{***⁽²⁰⁾} milk net production for sheep is (19678) tons , (4580) for goats and (6732) tons for cows, The net production in AL-Anbar (30990) tons. The consumption of one person of milk in 2020 (52) kg/ year as shown in table (1). The total consumption for the whole governorate (87909) tons versus a food gap (shortage) of (56919) tons and the self-sufficiency rate of milk is (35%) as shown in table (3) and Figure(3). Through the forgoing we see that the reason for the food gap (shortage) and not achieving self- sufficiency is because of the lack of producing cattle's of milk comparing with consumption size and the reason is non- availability of natural farms in all the year time and limiting them at rain season because the area lies in semidry lands which number and that oblige farmers to provide fodder and that increase the cost of stock farming and milk production and this make them work according to their financial ability.

Fish is a main source of food whether it is produced by fish farming or by water traps. Fish has nutritional value where it contains protein of a bout (70%) of its dry weight. It has a high amount of amino- acids which human body requires. They also contains salts and metals such as calcium, sodium, potassium, iodine and phosphorus. It considers digestible food and activates growth.⁽²¹⁾ The consumption of an individual from fish in 2020 is (9) kg as shown in table (1). The production of the governorate in the same year is (7518) tons of the all aquariums, cages and water traps as shown in table (3) and Figure(3) versus an average of consumption of (15215) tons the size of food gap is (7697) tons, and the average of self- sufficiency for the governorate for fish is (49%) the average of consumption and the lack of production is the reason of making food gap (shortage) therefore there should support to increase production to reach to the self- sufficiency stage.

Honey is foodstuff and drug it contains vitamins, amino acids, metals, sugars, they are mostly monocular, therefore beekeeping becomes a profitable resource and a financial resource indispensable for many beekeepers especially beekeeping doesn't need a big capital. The honey composition vary due to the vary of plants in farms whether natural plants or agricultural crops and flowers.⁽²²⁾ The average of consumption for an individual from honey in 2020 is (300) gm. as it shown in table (1) and the production of AL-Anbar governorate is (169231) kg while the consumption is (507165) kg recording food gap of about (337934) kg and an average of self- sufficiency for honey in AL-Anbar governorate of about (33%) as shown in table (3) and Figure(3). Through the foregoing it's clear that the governorate doesn't meet the average of consumption and that leads to food gap (shortage) and that needs increase the production by supporting beekeepers to achieve self-sufficiency.

Conclusions

1-AL-Anbar governorate achienced a rate of self-sufficiency for some crops and without food gap crops like wheat, corn vegetables, dates and onions and tubers. The reason of this is the expansion in planting these crops.

2- AL-Anbar governorate doesn't achieve self-sufficiency and there is food gap (shortage) in crops like barley, fruits, legumes and oil crops.

3- AL-Anbar governorate suffers from food gap (shortage) in all animal production which mean that the governorate doesn't have self-sufficiency and the reason is the lack of investment in animal production because most farmers depend on themselves in capitalizing their farms and the government support is few.

4- Throng the foregoing it is clear that AL-Anbar governorate achieved rate of self-sufficiency more than (100%) for plant production. The rate for wheat is (104%), for corn (109%), for vegetables (117%), for dates (364%), for onions and tubers (213%), while it achieves like barley (53%), fruit (12%), legumes (61%), and for oil crops (38%), which means there is food gap (shortage). The production must increase by using the avail ble potentials.

5- through the foregoing we can see that AL-Anbar governorate doesn't achieve a self-sufficiency rate more than (100%) in any kind of animal products and they are different, it achieves self-sufficiency rate for red meat of about (88%) while for chicken (61%) for eggs (49%) for honey (33%), this means that the governorate suffers from food gap (shortage) in all animal production and there must be support and expansion investment chances to reach the self-sufficiency, Through the foregoing we can say that the rate of self-sufficiency and food gap (shortage) for agricultural products, plants and animal in AL-Anbar governorate between production and consumption doesn't because of the increasing consumption by people but it is because of not developing

production in amount and kind to face the average of consumption in amount and kinds and here there is a must to exploit all the available resources like natural and human potentials to achieve self-sufficiency from food and get rid of food gap and to reach to food safety.

Recommendation

1- Expansion of investment in plant crops and livestock products in order to reach the self-sufficiency stage and prevent food gap (shortage).

2- The government supports farmers in order to increase production by expansion in agriculture and exploiting the available facilities.

Resources

Production

* Self-sufficiency = -----x100

References

Marwan Zohair Rajab, measuring self-sufficiency gap size for wheat in Iraq during (2001-2020), Baghdad college of economic sciences magazine, issue 38, 2014, page 150.

Mohammad Danial Muhsen Bshara, Emad mteer khleef, Arabic food security and its relationship with food aid, AL-Haqiqqa, magazine, first part, issue (10) 2007 page 280.

Ministry of planning and development cooperation, central statistical organization, population estimates for the year 2020 ad, unpublished datas.

Abdallah Najim AL-Nuami and others, production of summer farm crops, Ministry of higher education and scientific research, Baghdad, 1991 page 52.

Adnan AL-Qutb and others, fundamentals of producing fruits and vegetables, Damascus university printing press, Syria, 2011, page 278.

Alaee Dawood AL-Bitar, fruit trees fundamentals (planting – caring – producing) edition1, Al-Quds open university, 2015, page 4-5.

Abd-Al-Basit ouda Ibrahim zayed, date palm blunting and dates quality between habitat factors and care service programmes, edition1 Emirates publishing house, 2019, page 300.

Nabeel Ali Khaleel and Al-Mitwaly Abdallah Al-A Mitwaly and others, grains crops, edition 1, Al-Qahira press, 2015, page 174.

Ramadhan Masri Hillal, Abd Al-Wahed Abd Al-Hameed, oli crops agricultural transactions and pest control edition 1, Dar Al-Maaref for publishing and press, carion 2005, page 15.

Kadhim Ebadi Hamadi, livestock in Arab nation, edition 1, Dar Al-wadhah press, 2018, page 21.

Hussam Mowafaq Sabri, random importing effect of red meat in Iraqi red meat consumption, consumption, exploratory study Iraqi magazihe for research and consumer protection, Baghdad university, 5th part issue 2, 2012 page 117.

Ibrahim Sulaiman and Ahmed Mansour, animal production farms (economics and management edition 1, Dar Al-Fekr Al-Arabi cario, January 2008, page 101.

*The rate of the prepared for slaughter form the flock (55%) for sheep, (52%) for goats (54%) for cows.

Ministry of planning and cooperation development central statisticl organization average weight of carcasses, comprehensive survey for livestock in 2020, unpublished, datas.

Mohammed Ali Maki Al-Rubaiee, principles for animal production edition 1, Al-Noor press 2020 page, 7-8.

Clearance ration: is extracting un eaten parts from carcass like innards skins and so, and they differ among carcasses, it is for sheep (54%) for goats (52%) for cows (55%).

Nazar Abdallah Khatab, poultry managing, edition 2, Ministry of high education and scientific research, Mosul university, 2000, page 13.

interviewing some farms owners on 4/ 8/ 2021.

Fareed Fawzi Al-Shahwani and animal production, edition 1, Baghdad 1990, page 375.

Mohammed Ali Maki Al-Rubaiee, milk cattle production, edition 1, Al-Noor library 2018, page 39- 40.

Mohammed Khalifa Husein Al-Duluimi, population and food in Iraq 1957-1977, PhD thesis (unpublished) college of literature Baghdad university 1981, page 182-183.

*(23%)sheep, (25%) goats, (197%) cows.

**milk amount in a year for sheep (60)kg /year for goats (180) kg/year for cows (788) kg/ year.

Ministry of planning and cooperation development, central statistical organization national accounts, comprehensive livestock survey, 2020, unpublished datas. ***Exclude breast feeding category for sheep (53%) for goats (66%) for cows (79%).

Mohamaed Mahmoud Al-Sayad, Al introduction in economic geography, Dar Al-Nahdha, Al-Arabia, Beirut, 1971, page 193.

Mitwaly Mustafa Khattab, honey bees (products, stractures, natural benefits) edition 1 Dar Al-Kotob Al-Arabia, 2000, page 290-298.

Ministry of planning and cooperation development, central statistical organization national accounts, comprehensive livestock survey, 2020, unpublished datas

Ministry of Agriculture, Al-Anbar governorate agriculture directorate, planning and follow-up department, 2020 unpublished datas.

Author Information

Mr. Nabeel Taha Ali Belal

University Of Anbar, College of education for
human Sciences

Prof. Dr Khalid Akbar Abdullah

University Of Anbar, College of education for human
Sciences
